

The fact that nitrate is not in co-ordination sphere was further confirmed by the conductance shown by chelate in alcoholic solution.

Hence the molecular formula of Ca-Lawsone chelate and Zn-Lawsone chelate are $[(C_{10}H_5O_3)(Ca)(C_2H_5OH)_2]^+NO_3^-$ and $[(C_{10}H_5O_3)(Zn)(C_2H_5OH)_2]^+NO_3^-$ respectively.

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Application of Thermographic Analysis in the Studies of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds Effect of Accelerators and Antioxidant

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Manuscript received 7 February 1975; revised 5 July 1975;
accepted 11 August 1975

EARLIER reports illustrated the effects of (i) replacement of natural rubber by reclaim in a compound¹, (ii) increment of the preparation of sulphur in an accelerated reclaim mix² and (iii) stearic

acid and zinc oxide in accelerated high-as well as low-sulphur reclaim compound². The effects of (a) changing the type of accelerator in high- and low-sulphur reclaim compounds and (b) an antioxidant on a representative reclaim compound as well as on the reclaim are the subjects of this communication.

Effect of Accelerators

The recipe of these high- and low-sulphur compounds are shown in Table I, their DTA thermograms being shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively, Curves A, B, C, D, E (Figure 1) and a, b, c, d, e (Figure 2) represent respectively the high- and low-sulphur compounds using different types of accelerators.

In the case of high-sulphur compounds Tm of sulphur (monoclinic) around 110°-120° has been exhibited more or less prominently in different accelerator systems, accompanied, in some cases, by the Tm of stearic acid and zinc stearate as has been observed previously². Similar observations have been noted in low-sulphur compounds. The primary exotherm appears to be principally due to the curing in the case of high-sulphur systems, but the profiles of the curves for different systems containing different accelerators exhibit their own characteristics quite clearly. Peak height in case of high-sulphur compounds remains practically unchanged, although this parameter gradually increases in the order DPG < MBT < CBS < TMTD < BA in low-sulphur compounds. The height of increase of high-sulphur compounds (that are almost identical irrespective of the type of accelerator used) lies approximately intermediate between the maximum and minimum value of peak height in the low-sulphur compounds. Fractional peak area as used²⁻⁴ and stated² earlier, in case of high-sulphur compound are almost the same in case of BA and TMTD accelerator systems (curves A and E) whereas in the remaining systems like DPG, MBT and CBS (curves B, C, D) this area is of comparable magnitude, but somewhat different from that of the previous two

TABLE I—FORMULATION OF HIGH- AND LOW-SULPHUR COMPOUNDS** ANALYSED BY DTA

	High-sulphur					Low-sulphur				
	A	B	C	D	E	a	b	c	d	e
Reclaim	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Zinc oxide	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
BA††	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—
DPG†	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—
MBT*	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—
CBS‡	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5	—
TMTD‡‡	—	—	—	—	0.5	—	—	—	—	0.5
Sulphur	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5

** Formulation are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim

†† Butyraldehyde aniline

† Diphenylguanidine

* 2-Mercaptobenzothiazole

‡ N-cyclohexyl benzothiazole-2-sulphonamide

‡‡ Tetramethylthiuram disulphide.

systems. In low-sulphur systems, however, this parameter has similar values in case of BA and TMTD accelerator systems (curves a and e), and the

Fig. 1. Effect of different accelerators in high-sulphur reclaim compounds

Fig. 2. Effect of different accelerators in low-sulphur reclaim compounds.

value of this area in the case of the other three systems (DPG, MBT, CBS; curves b, c, d) inspite of exhibiting a small difference within themselves, is considerably lower than that of the previous systems (BA and TMTD). Initiation temperature (T_i) stands

Fig. 3. Effect of antioxidant in a reclaim compound (A, a) and the reclaim (B, b). B'—Material left after separation of the acetone extract from the reclaim (B).

between 140° and 175° in high-sulphur compounds for different accelerators, whereas this range is compressed to 160° – 170° in low-sulphur systems. In high-sulphur systems no significant difference is observed in the peak temperature (T_p) for different accelerators. On the other hand, in low-sulphur systems T_p does not show appreciable difference between the systems like DPG, MBT and CBS. T_p , similar in BA and TMTD, was, however, considerably higher than that in either of the above three systems. In each accelerator system T_p in low-sulphur compounds has been found to be higher than that of the corresponding high-sulphur compounds. Also a break in the slope of the rising peaks in low-sulphur systems has been observed at approximately the peak temperature of the corresponding high-sulphur systems. Peak slope in all high-sulphur systems was greater than that of the corresponding low-sulphur systems, the slope difference being small in case of BA (curves, A, a) and TMTD (curves, E, e), and well-marked in DPG, MBT and CBS (curves B, b; C, c; and D, d).

Next to the above exotherm the thermal patterns in high-sulphur systems show some similarities in trends at different temperatures for different accelerator systems. In low-sulphur systems, however, a secondary peak is observed with varying prominence in the different systems, the correspondence of such peaks in temperature being shown in pairs like BA

and TMTD, DPG and MBT. In the case of CBS, apart from the general similarities mentioned above, some prominent difference is also noticed in the higher temperature region.

Effect of Antioxidant

Table 2 represents the recipe of the two pairs of systems whose DTA thermograms are shown in Figure 3, curves A and a represent respectively the reclaim compound and that with antioxidant. Curves B and b, on the other hand, stand for the reclaim itself and the same plus antioxidant respectively, whereas curve B' represents the material left after removal of the acetone-extract from the reclaim.*

TABLE 2—FORMULATION OF SYSTEMS** ANALYSED BY DTA

	A	a	B	b
Reclaim	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Stearic acid	0.5	0.5	—	—
Zinc oxide	2.5	2.5	—	—
TMTD††	0.5	0.5	—	—
Sulphur	1.5	1.5	—	—
PBN††	—	0.5	—	0.5

††Tetramethylthiuram disulphide

†† Phenylbetanaphthylamine.

** Formulations are based on 50% hydrocarbon content of reclaim.

In the compounds A and a in the region of 140° a break is observed in both the compounds, the break being well-marked and comparatively short respectively in the compounds with and without antioxidant. As per the primary exotherm both in the case of the compound and the reclaim itself there is no appreciable change in the initiation temperature (Ti) on adding the antioxidant to either of the systems, although the pair of compounds have a lower Ti than that of the reclaim. Peak temperature (Tp) also diminishes in the compound as well as in the reclaim base when antioxidant is added to either of them, the compound with and without the antioxidant, however, showing their Tp values to be respectively lower than those the reclaim with and without the same antioxidant. Peak height remains practically unchanged in the compound on addition of antioxidant, which, however, acts quite effectively in the reclaim itself to bring down its peak height. Fractional peak area²⁻⁴ decreases by a small degree in the compound, but appreciably in the reclaim, by using the antioxidant. The antioxidant, however, imparted a much higher change in the peak slope in case of the reclaim than that in the compound based on it.

On the other hand, on separation of the acetone extract from the reclaim, the residual matter exhibits

* Commercial data specifying the reclaim (WTR100) is as follows :

Ash, %	Acetone % Extract,	Carbon % black,	Rubber hydrocarbon by difference, %
10±2	14±4	22±4	Not less than 50

somewhat different characteristics (curve B'). Thus Ti is considerably lowered, Tp is also lowered to some extent. Peak height increases appreciably but peak area is not measured as there is no proper resolution. Moreover, there is no fixed slope from the point of initiation to the peak. The acetone extract is known to contain usually the extender oils (for synthetic hydrocarbons) and process oils (and minor amounts of depolymerized rubber, accelerator, antioxidant residues, etc.).

The portion suggesting a secondary peak above 300° in case of the reclaim does not appear in case of the material left after acetone-extraction. Since the major fraction of the acetone-extract is oil, it may be attributed to the thermal behaviour of the oil (and the rubber). Therefore, on treating the original reclaim with the antioxidant, the nature of the disappearance of this secondary peak may be due mainly to the prevention of the oxidative degradation of the rubber, partly to the thermal degradation of the rubber and partly to the reaction of the antioxidant with the oils present. Similar, but more prominent, elimination of such secondary peak is also observed when the reclaim compound is treated with the antioxidant.

Detailed investigations are in progress and will be published later on.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R. for the award of a senior research fellowship. The author also wishes to thank Professor S. R. Palit, Dr. S. N. Bhattacharyya, M/S. Escon Consultants Pvt. Ltd., Calcutta, Department of Applied Chemistry (Calcutta University) and M/S Alkali and Chemical Corporation of India Ltd., Rishra, West Bengal for their encouragement and help in various capacities.

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Metal Complexes of Some β -Ketoimines and Salicylaldimines

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Manuscript received 20 February 1975; revised 7 August 1975;
accepted 8 August 1975

BETA-Ketoimine and salicylaldimine complexes are expected to be similar due to the common O-N donor atom set of each ligand system and the presence of conjugated six-membered chelate ring in them. Recently Holm¹ *et al.* and Yamada² *et al.* have reviewed the metal complexes.

A perusal of the literature has revealed that much work has not been done on anthranilic acid and β -alanine Schiff bases with Benzoylacetone and